

**DEVELOPMENT OF A REAL TIME AUGMENTED REALITY MAKEUP
VISUALISATION SYSTEM**

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CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that Adekola, Mariam Omoriyeba carried out this project in the Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Osun State, Nigeria.

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DEDICATION

This project is dedicated to Almighty Allah, who allowed me to complete my five-year program, my loving family and friends, for their unwavering support, encouragement, and belief in my abilities throughout this journey and also to computer science and engineering students all around the world to keep contributing and making awesome achievements.

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GLOSSARY

(List of Acronyms and Abbreviations)

AMS	Augmented Makeup System
AR	Augmented Reality
ASM	Active Shape Models
BGR	Blue, Green and Red
CIELAB	A colour space defined by the International Commission on Illumination (Commission Internationale de l'Éclairage in French) (CIE), used to represent colours based on their lightness (L), position along the red-green axis (A), and position along the blue-yellow axis (B).
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
FPS	Frames Per Second
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HEX	Hexadecimal
Lab	Also known as “LAB”; an acronym for CIELAB.
MTCNN	Multi-Task Cascaded Convolutional Networks
OpenCV	Open Source Computer Vision Library
RGB	Red, Green and Blue
SVM	Support Vector Machines
STD	Standard Deviation
UML	Unified Modelling Language

ABSTRACT

This project presents the development of a Real Time Augmented Reality Makeup Visualization System, aimed at enabling users to visualise makeup on their faces accurately and in real time. It was developed using Python programming language, incorporating the use of MediaPipe, Streamlit, and OpenCV. The development phase involved requirements elicitation, system design and implementation and thorough evaluation of system performance and user engagement levels.

The study outlines the methodologies used, ranging from stakeholder interviews to Unified Modelling Language (UML) diagrams, which aided in understanding user needs and designing the system's architecture.

User engagement levels were evaluated through face landmark analysis, including eye gaze direction, eyebrow movement, lip curvature, and smile intensity. Results revealed that the majority of users displayed a high level of engagement, indicating a success rate of approximately 91.8% in accurately aligning virtual makeup with users' faces. Additionally, the system's percentage of successfully tracked frames before and during makeup application was evaluated under different scenarios.

The system is relevant to diverse application areas, such as education and the cosmetic industry, offering innovative ways to explore makeup options virtually. Recommendations for future improvements include addressing challenges faced during development, optimizing the system for mobile devices, and enhancing user engagement through ongoing user interaction analysis and feedback incorporation.

Keywords: Augmented Reality, Makeup Visualization, Computer Vision, User Engagement, Real Time Application, Facial Tracking, User Interaction.

CHAPTER ONE

1. INTRODUCTION

This chapter covers the background of the study, the problem statement, the scope of the project, the aim and objectives of the project as well as a brief overview of the methodology used and the organisation of this report.

1.1. Background of Study

Makeup is a widely-used skill to improve one's facial appearance (Zhang *et al.*, 2019) and is especially used by women. Guo & Sim, (2009) added that makeup is used for beautification purposes and is the process of applying cosmetic products, such as foundation, powder, and cream, which are non-permanent, as opposed to plastic surgery (Rathgeb *et al.*, 2019). While traditional makeup techniques have been used for decades, recent advances in technology have led to the development of digital makeup. Guo & Sim, (2009) defined digital makeup as the use of technology to apply makeup, creating an experience that is analogous to traditional makeup. In recent years, the use of virtual makeup software to experiment with various makeup looks in pictures or short videos has become increasingly popular (Zhang *et al.*, 2019). According to a definition by Merriam-Webster Inc. (n.d.), Augmented Reality (AR) is a technology that allows users to experience a digital overlay of information and images superimposed onto the physical world in real time. In short, Augmented Reality technology allows users to merge the real and virtual worlds, creating immersive experiences that are augmented by technology (Klopfer & Sheldon, 2010; Dede, 2009). Research studies have explored different approaches to achieving desired makeup looks virtually using deep learning techniques such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) for tasks including facial feature

extraction, region segmentation, and Generative Adversarial Network methods (GAN) (Zhan *et al.*, 2016; Ma *et al.*, 2021). These advancements have enabled the development of AR applications for makeup try-on, tutorials, and education. According to Nguyen *et al.* (2021), makeup try-on is a vital application in both retail and entertainment. Kim & Forsythe, (2008) reported that virtual try-on technology has been developed for commercial purposes in two significant forms: avatar-based simulations and photo-based try-on. At retail store cosmetics counters and even online stores, makeup simulation systems are employed to assist shoppers in selecting cosmetics (Iwabuchi *et al.*, 2009). With these systems, customers may quickly and easily see how the selected product looks on them.

Furthermore, Javornik *et al.* (2016) created a Magic Mirror solution utilized in smart device applications for digital makeup applications, and Leong *et al.* (2023) designed a system that integrates with video conferencing applications and enables users to privately apply AR filters such as makeup on themselves or on others using facial tracking and re-rendering techniques during a video call. Different approaches have been studied to achieve virtual makeup looks. Facial Makeup Transfer Generation, for instance, transfers the makeup style from a well-suited reference image to a face without makeup, allowing models to suggest the most suitable makeup for the user and transfer it to their face in an image (Liu *et al.*, 2016; Zhang *et al.*, 2019). Huang *et al.* (2021) proposed an end-to-end Identity Preservation makeup transfer system based on generative adversarial networks (GANs) that allowed for the transfer of the makeup style, while preserving the background as well as the critical patterns of the original identity of a reference makeup style onto an input face image in real time.

However, there has been a recent shift towards exploring traditional image processing techniques in the development of makeup visualisation systems. Kose *et al.* (2015)

proposed a facial makeup detector that extracts a feature vector that captures the shape and texture characteristics of the input face. Jang *et al.* (2013) also used traditional techniques, such as colour space conversion, thresholding, and filtering, to enable real time makeup simulation without requiring a reference image. This shift is likely due to the complexity and computational requirements of deep learning algorithms, as well as the need for more interpretable and explainable systems in the field of cosmetic makeup. Virtual makeup application methods eliminate the use of model images (Borges & Morimoto, 2019).

Furthermore, according to Forbes (Arthur, 2017), AR technology has been implemented by several cosmetic brands, such as L'Oreal and Sephora, in their marketing strategies to allow customers to virtually try-on makeup products and provide a more interactive and immersive shopping experience.

Both traditional image processing techniques and deep learning algorithms have been crucial in the development of makeup try-on systems, which have come a long way from the days of trying out products in-store. The development has been particularly evident in recent years, with studies such as those by Jang *et al.* (2013), Javornik *et al.* (2016) and Leong *et al.* (2023) showcasing the potential of AR technology in makeup visualisation systems. These techniques have helped to refine the systems, providing users with an effective and intuitive tool for exploring and experimenting with different makeup looks.

Building on this exciting field of research, this project is based on the use of image processing and AR techniques to develop a real time makeup visualisation system that will provide a solution that is accurate, versatile, and user-friendly.

1.2 Problem Statement

Despite the growing number of virtual try-on applications, currently available solutions for face accessories present some limitations. Many applications show the results of the virtual scene in a static 2D image, which limits interactivity (Marelli *et al.*, 2022), and thereby lacks real time visualisation capabilities. Many AR makeup applications do not allow users to customise the intensity or placement of the makeup. This can make it difficult for users to accurately assess the appearance of the makeup and also for makeup artists to provide personalised recommendations to achieve a natural look. As a result, there is a need for a system that allows users to see how different makeup styles will look on their faces in real time, enabling them to make cost-effective and informed decisions within a short time.

1.3 Scope of the Project

The scope of this project is limited to providing a real time makeup simulation tool that is operated through a user interface. This project would track the user's facial features and model makeup application techniques on the face in real time with the ability to save the finished makeup look.

1.4 Justification

Traditionally, trying on makeup has been done through physical application or with the help of photo editing software which can be time-consuming and tedious respectively (Guo & Sim, 2009). AR technology in cosmetics can promote sustainable consumption (**SDG #12 - Responsible Consumption and Production**) by allowing customers to virtually try-on makeup, saving time and also reducing waste from unsuitable purchases and returns. It would also help makeup artists with recommending styles to their clients. Thus, it positively impacts sustainability and customer satisfaction.

1.5 Aim and Objectives

The aim of this project is to develop a system that can visualise makeup on users in augmented reality and can function in real time.

The specific objectives are to:

- i. Elicit the requirements of the augmented reality makeup visualisation system.
- ii. Design the proposed model of the system based on the requirements outlined in (i);
- iii. Implement the makeup visualisation system based on (ii); and
- iv. Evaluate the performance of the system implemented in (iii).

1.6 Organisation of Report

The following gives an outline of the contents of this report.

Chapter one includes the background of the project, the problem statement, aim and objectives, the scope of the study, and the justification of the project.

Chapter two reviews existing literature on augmented makeup application systems explaining their strengths and limitations. Concepts which are relevant to the study were also defined.

Chapter three thoroughly comprises a detailed explanation of the methodology used in the implementation of this project, showing relevant UML diagrams such as the class diagram, etc.

Chapter four discusses the implementation of the project as well as the results obtained during evaluation of the system.

Chapter five concludes the project, giving an overview of what has been done and suggesting recommendations for future work.

CHAPTER TWO

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

This chapter discusses the comprehensive overview of the study and analysis of already existing systems, related work and proposed systems. It would also describe the theoretical concepts and basic principles behind the study.

2.2 Conceptual Review

2.2.1 Augmented Makeup System (AMS)

Augmented Makeup System is commonly called Virtual Try-on System. Augmented Reality enables customers to interact dynamically with systems, serving as an information processing tool (Hilken *et al.*, 2017). Borges & Morimoto (2019) enhanced the virtual mirror experience by using a physical applicator, such as a finger or an object of similar shape, to apply virtual makeup.

The traditional steps of a typical makeup application system include (Hung *et al.*, 2020):

- i. Input an image or pre-recorded video of the face for detection and feature points identification.
- ii. Facial features such as eyes, eyebrows, nose and lips based on identified points are segmented into makeup regions.
- iii. Application of cosmetic colour to the makeup regions.

- iv. Coloured regions are integrated back into the original input.

Virtual try-on applications offer customers the opportunity to digitally try-on makeup, providing a useful tool for making informed purchasing decisions (Quantumrun Foresight, 2022). Creating a virtual try-on system poses several difficulties, such as determining how to present the try-on results to the user (Marelli *et al.*, 2022). They also pointed out that the item selected by the user can be displayed in real time or in a deferred mode. In real time, a live-feed video is often used as it allows the user to move around and see how the item fits them and interacts with the system. In deferred mode, a pre-recorded video is shown to the user who can watch it. This video can be generated offline, but the user's interaction with the system is limited.

2.2.2 Digital Makeup

Digital makeup refers to the use of technology, which could be either a phone or webcam, to apply beauty cosmetics to enhance one's appearance, analogous to traditional face makeup (Guo & Sim, 2009). The technique allows individuals to change their appearance using virtual products instead of physical ones.

Huang *et al.* (2021) defined automatic digital makeup in their study as desirable because people are eager to obtain a more effective and efficient beautiful picture to keep up with social media status.

According to Quantumrun Foresight (2022), digital makeup has diverse applications such as:

- i. Virtual makeup for video calls on apps like Zoom, Snapchat and Twitch.
- ii. e-commerce companies adding filters to facial recognition systems for payment in e-commerce.

- iii. Media and advertising companies use this technology to alter or conceal the physical appearance of their actors or reporters during or after a media production, both for images and video.

Figures 2.1 and 2.2 provide visual representations of the effects and application of digital makeup.

Figure 2.1 showcases a comparison between the before and after application of digital makeup.

The figure demonstrates the application of different types of digital makeup on distinct areas of the face. For instance, foundation is virtually applied to the skin region, blush is applied to the cheeks, and lipstick is applied to the lips, as well as the appropriate makeup is applied to the other indicated areas.

Figure 2.2 presents (left) the anatomy of the face relevant to makeup application, highlighting various face parts such as the eyes, nose, lips, and other skin areas and on the right side, a traditionally made-up face is displayed, demonstrating the application of makeup on different facial areas.

Figure 2.1 Comparison between before and after digital makeup application

Figure 2.2 Face Anatomy for Makeup Application (left) and Traditional Face Makeup (right)

2.2.3 Face Tracking

Facial tracking is the process of detecting and monitoring the movement of a person's face in real time, which is essential for the accurate application of virtual makeup. This is often done using computer vision algorithms and is used in various applications such as augmented reality, video conferencing, and virtual makeup applications. Face detection involves classifying sub-windows in images as either face or non-face and further recognizing the unique characteristics of individual faces (Li & Jain, 2005). This technology is used in a variety of applications, including security systems, photo tagging, and human-computer interaction. The face detection process typically begins with an image or video being preprocessed to identify potential face regions. This is done by using techniques such as edge detection and blob analysis to identify areas that are likely to contain faces. Next, the face detection algorithms use a combination of geometric and statistical features, against various cues. According to Li and Jain (2005), such cues include skin colour, motion, facial shape, facial appearance, or a combination of these factors. Once the faces have been detected, they can be further processed to perform tasks in various fields such as makeup transfer. Zhang *et al.* (2016) stated that numerous face applications, including face recognition and facial expression analysis, depend on accurate face detection and alignment. There are various methods for face detection, including traditional computer vision-based methods and deep learning-based methods.

Here are a few face detection methods highlighted briefly in a tabular form, as shown in Table 2.1.

Table 2.1 Some Methods of Face Detection and Literature Reference

Year	Methods	Relevant Paper Title	Authors
1998	SVM-based face detection	Support Vector Machines Applied to Face Recognition	Phillips <i>et al.</i>
2001	Haar-based face detection	Rapid Object Detection using a Boosted Cascade of Simple Features	Viola and Jones
2015	Deep learning-based face detection - Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)	A Convolutional Neural Network Cascade for Face Detection	Li <i>et al.</i>
2016	Multi-Task Cascaded Convolutional Networks (MTCNN)	Joint Face Detection and Alignment using Multi-task Cascaded Convolutional Networks	Zhang <i>et al.</i>

Real time face detection is an important component in many computer vision and biometric applications, such as facial recognition, video surveillance, and human-computer interaction. The ability to detect faces in real time is crucial for these applications to be usable and effective. According to Datta *et al.*, (2016), a real time face detection system is designed to quickly and accurately detect faces in images or videos in real time with high precision or very low latency. To perform real time face detection, fast and efficient algorithms are needed to scan images and identify faces within them. One of the most well-known systems that accomplish this is the Viola-Jones face detector. In the case of video, the detected faces may need to be tracked using a face-tracking component (Li & Jain, 2005). Machine learning-based methods use trained models to identify faces in images and videos, for example, the Viola-Jones algorithm and the Single Shot MultiBox Detector (SSD) method, while feature-based methods extract specific features from images or videos and use these features to locate faces. Feature-based methods, such as the Scale-Invariant Feature Transform (SIFT) and the Speeded Up Robust Features (SURF) algorithm, are also used for real time face detection.

2.2.4 BlazeFace Algorithm

MediaPipe BlazeFace is a real time face detection and face tracking algorithm developed by Google's MediaPipe team. It is designed to detect and track faces in video streams or images using deep neural networks. The BlazeFace algorithm has two main components: a face detection model and a face landmark model.

The face detection model first identifies the location of all the faces in the input image or video frame, while the landmark model then estimates the facial landmarks for each detected face. The face detection model is based on a lightweight, single-shot object

detection architecture called the BlazeFace network. It uses a deep Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) to predict the location of faces in an input image or video frame. This network is optimized for real time performance on mobile and embedded devices, with a small memory footprint and low computational requirements. Once the face detection model has identified the location of a face in an input image or video frame, the landmark model estimates the 6 degrees of freedom pose (i.e., position, orientation, and scale) of the face, as well as 468 facial landmarks, such as the corners of the eyes, the tip of the nose, and the corners of the mouth. The MediaPipe BlazeFace algorithm is an effective and efficient face tracking component that can be used in a variety of applications, including virtual makeup try-on, face recognition, and emotion analysis. Figure 2.3 showcases an illustration of the practical application of MediaPipe for object detection, emphasising the key stages involved in the process.

Figure 2.3 Object detection using MediaPipe (Lugaresi et al., 2019)

2.2.5 Image Preprocessing

Various image processing techniques can be used to enhance or modify images for different applications. One such technique is image filtering, which can be used to reduce noise or enhance edges in an image (Plain English, n.d.). There are different types of filters available, including average blurring, median filtering, Gaussian filter, bilateral filter, alpha blending, sharpness, brightness, contrast, saturation, Poisson editing, sigma filter, Gabor filter, Sobel filter, Prewitt filter, Laplacian filter, Teager filter, range filter, Standard Deviation (STD) filter, box filter, mean filter, and Gaussian filter (MicroImages, n.d.).

Smoothing Filters

Smoothing filters are used to remove noise in images and are usually applied in the preprocessing step. These include:

I. Poisson Editing

It was introduced in 2003 and is becoming a technique with major applications in many different domains of image processing and computer graphics (Pérez *et al.*, 2003)

II. Sigma Filter

This filter is motivated by the sigma probability of the Gaussian distribution. It smooths the image noise by averaging only those neighbourhood pixels which have the intensities within a fixed sigma range of the centre pixel.

Consequently, image edges are preserved, and subtle details and thin lines such as roads are retained.

III. Gaussian Filter

When using a Gaussian filter to suppress noise in an image, the filter smooths

out the noise but can also distort the underlying signal. The two-dimensional digital Gaussian filter can be expressed as

$$G(x, y) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma^2}} \exp\left(-\frac{(x^2 + y^2)}{2\sigma^2}\right) \quad (2.1)$$

while the one-dimensional Gaussian filter is expressed as

$$G(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma}} \exp\left(-\frac{x^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \quad (2.2)$$

where:

- i. x and y are random variables
- ii. G(x,y) is the value of the Gaussian filter at position (x,y).
- iii. G(x) is the value of the Gaussian filter value at point x.
- iv. π is the mathematical constant Pi (approximately 3.14159).
- v. σ is the standard deviation of the Gaussian distribution, controlling the spread of the filter.
- vi. exp is the exponential function, the base of the natural logarithm (approximately 2.71828).

and the size of the filter kernel, l ($-1 \leq x, y \leq 1$) is often determined by omitting values lower than five per cent of the maximum value of the kernel.

(Deng & Cahill, 1993).

IV. Bilateral Filter

A bilateral filter is used for smoothening images and reducing noise while preserving edges.

V. Median Filter

Median filtering is a nonlinear process useful in reducing impulsive, or salt-and-pepper noise. The median filter is also used to preserve edge properties while reducing the noise.

Finally, gradient filters, such as Sobel and Prewitt filters, are useful for detecting edges in an image, while the Teager filter is used for edge detection and feature extraction (MicroImages, n.d).

2.2.6 Augmented Reality Filters

Many popular video conferencing applications support the use of AR-based effects, commonly referred to as AR Filters. Augmented Reality filters can provide means to help people picture something new by changing what they see, rather than requiring them to rely on their mind's eye. Superimposing virtual elements on camera streams has become a popular feature in video-calling (e.g., Zoom, Microsoft Teams) as well as social media applications (e.g. Snapchat, Instagram). These apply image manipulations on a live video source based on head/face position tracking. One popular use of AR is to change the appearance of one's background. Virtual backgrounds are a type of AR filter since body tracking is required to segment the background from the foreground. Another subset of AR filters is AR Face Filters, which can change the appearance of oneself to various degrees. These effects can range from adding simple accessories on a person, to completely transforming their appearance to look like another character (Leong *et al.*, 2023).

2.3 Related Work

Hung *et al.*, (2020) proposed a new virtual makeup system that uses a Python library, Dlib. The system features an offline database known as the "Golden Sample," which

consists of facial components represented by shape vectors. The online makeup process includes face detection and landmark point identification on the input image. The best matching pattern approach was employed which involves estimating the minimum distance between the identified landmarks and a single corresponding feature vector of the samples in the Golden Sample. The best-matched pattern then guides the selection of the best shape representations for the makeup target, which are transformed and coloured before being stitched onto the user's image to complete the makeup look. Similar to this project, the users can choose the specific facial region to apply the colour and the desired cosmetic colour to be applied in the system. However, this work explicitly demonstrated the application of lipstick as a form of makeup and exhibits satisfactory efficiency. Face detection and landmark identification play crucial roles likewise in this project, ensuring accurate placement of the makeup. Unlike this project, the authors used a dataset to employ the use of a matching pattern and the Dlib Python library for landmarks identification instead of MediaPipe Python library. In addition, their solution was limited in real time capability as it made use of static images for implementation.

Park *et al.*, (2018) developed an automatic virtual makeup system as an innovative approach to virtual makeup recommendation by leveraging the user's skin tone as a primary factor in determining the best makeup style. The system relies on a comprehensive database of colour samples from the four general seasons (Winter, Spring, Summer, and Autumn) to perform colour analysis and makeup recommendations. The facial landmark extraction process involves the use of the Dlib Machine Learning Algorithm to accurately detect key features, such as the iris, hair, and skin colour, similar to the previous work discussed above. The landmarks data is used to determine the user's personal colour by applying various techniques, including Circle

Hough Transform, K-means clustering, Canny Edge detection, morphological closing, and conversion to the Lab domain. The personal colour is then classified into one of the four seasons based on warm and cool tones, with spring and autumn assigned as warm tones and summer and winter as cool tones. The recommended makeup style is determined by matching the user's personal colour with makeup methods from the database, which takes into consideration various factors such as gender, age, and type of makeup. The application of makeup is done in a precise manner, with the use of 1-D interpolation and conversion to the Lab domain to define the skin region in Red, Green, and Blue (RGB) boundaries and effectively colouring. A Gaussian blur filter is also applied to achieve a more natural effect, hence a good reason for adopting the technique in this project. Overall, this study represents a significant contribution to the field of virtual makeup recommendation, with its use of machine learning algorithms and personalised colour analysis as key strengths. The results of the study demonstrate the feasibility of creating a virtual makeup system that effectively matches a user's skin tone, providing more accurate and relevant recommendations, a feature which is not included in this project. However, despite the use of a new approach, this work had limited scope, using a narrow sample of individuals with limited skin tones and hair colours.

Treepong *et al.*, (2018) presented a novel interactive face makeup system that allows users to practice makeup application without physical makeup tools. The authors conducted a survey to identify general makeup behaviours and difficulties, which helped in developing hardware prototypes of makeup tools, including lipstick and eyebrow brushes, to create a realistic feeling. These mockup makeup tools can be controlled via an Arduino Uno board and a monitor. Mathematical methods were used to ensure precision in the mockup tools by estimating the relationship between the marker and the makeup tool's tip. A 3D model of the human face was created using Unity 3D

framework, and real time tracking of 33 facial feature points was done with Kinect. The system was evaluated based on the tools created and the general system functionality. The users' satisfaction with the makeup tools was assessed through questionnaire distribution. The system was found to be effective with users reporting high levels of satisfaction with the makeup tools. However, the use of Arduino in this study introduces limitations in terms of portability, which is a key advantage of the AR makeup visualisation system developed in the proposed system. Despite the common goal of providing a virtual makeup experience, both systems employ distinct methodologies and techniques. This project emphasises real time digital makeup application. On the other hand, hardware prototypes of makeup tools and a 3D model for makeup practice are employed in this study, demonstrating a different approach to achieving the virtual makeup experience.

Dhall *et al.*, (2009) presented a system for automatic digital makeup application which did not rely on user input. The system was based on two parameters: ethnicity-based skin tone and the created dataset was performed using a fuzzy decision classification algorithm. The dataset consisted of sample images, hue and saturation information of skin tone for each ethnicity type and gender, and the type of makeup to be applied. Secondly, facial components such as lips, eyes, and mouth were extracted from the segmented blob using the Haar feature-based Viola-Jones face detector and the Intel OpenCV library. Ethnicity classification was executed using kernel-based Support Vector Machines (SVM) with the LIBSVM library. Gender classification was performed using the AdaBoost algorithm, and for lips and eye extraction, the Active Shape Models (ASM) algorithm was employed to match the ASM to the input image. Image processing techniques such as Gaussian smoothing and colour balancing were also used in the digital makeup phase. Finally, colour matching was performed based on

the predefined target makeup information and colour information from the database, considering the two underlying factors of the system. However, the system's lack of user customisation was a limitation as makeup may fit differently for each individual, unlike in this project. This project offers a personalised experience, allowing users to see how makeup suits their unique facial features. In summary, while both systems use machine learning and image processing for makeup application, they differ significantly in terms of user customization.

Guo and Sim (2009) proposed a digital face makeup system that was based on an example image. Their method incorporated the image of a face with makeup as an example and maps the makeup to a target face in a seamless manner. This involved segmenting the image of the target face and extracting the features of the example makeup image. The makeup transfer is achieved through a non-linear optimization process which minimises the difference between the target face and the mapped makeup features. The results of their experiments showed that the proposed method produces realistic makeup transfer results. The authors' work laid the foundation for this project by using image processing techniques and optimization methods for digital makeup transfer. One essential technique employed is face segmentation, for which MediaPipe functionality was adopted in this project. Their proposed method demonstrated the ability to transfer makeup from an example image to a target image and generate various makeup styles with a single example. The inspiration drawn from their work guided the selection and design of the makeup filters in this project, allowing for seamless and natural-looking makeup application in real time. While both systems employ similar image processing techniques, the main distinction lies in their real time makeup application capability.

Kim & Forsythe (2008) developed a virtual try-on technology for commercial

purposes, offering two forms: avatar-based simulations and photo-based try-on. The avatar-based simulations involved trying on products using a virtual representative resembling the user's features, which users could then manipulate. In the photo-based try-on, products were superimposed on user-uploaded photos, providing a static 2D experience. Their work aimed to demonstrate how users would look with various products, including makeup, glasses, and apparel, by placing the items on uploaded user photos or customised avatars. Their technology catered to a broader range of products and relied on traditional computer graphics and virtual try-on techniques. In contrast, this project is specifically designed for makeup visualisation. It is based on real time video form, employing machine learning, and computer vision techniques to create a realistic and personalised makeup visualisation experience.

2.4 Existing System

An existing system from which the model of this system was designed is shown in Figure 2.4. It is a new virtual makeup system that features an offline database known as the "Golden Sample," which consists of facial components represented by shape vectors. The online makeup process includes face detection and landmark point identification on the input image and the use of the Dlib library, which is not being adopted in this project for greater efficiency.

2.5 Developed Model

The framework model for the proposed system is shown in Figure 2.5. The system gets a video input stream from the camera using the MediaPipe Library based on the BlazeFace Algorithm for face detection.

Subsequently, the facial tracker tracks the detected frame in real time and makeup regions are identified with marked feature points. Image processing techniques would

be applied and then colour selection is done before makeup is rendered on the user's face in augmented reality.

Figure 2.4 Model of Existing System (Hung et al., 2020)

Figure 2.5 Model of Real Time Augmented Reality Makeup Visualisation System using MediaPipe Framework

CHAPTER THREE

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

Many real time systems are concerned with collecting data from the system's environment, then transforming that data from its original representation into some other digital representation that can be more readily analysed and processed by the system (Sommerville, 2011). Realtime augmented reality makeup application systems allow users to virtually try different makeup looks and make adjustments in real time using a device with a camera, such as a desktop computer, a smartphone or a tablet. This chapter discusses the methodology of the system which includes the model used for developing the system, and system requirements. Building a software product is a process consisting of several distinct stages (Despa, 2014). Development processes include all of the activities involved in system development such as requirements definition, system design, hardware and software engineering, system integration, and testing. This chapter includes presentations of the various tools used by the Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC) phases and the rules and guidelines used in achieving the software methodology phases for the visualisation system would be covered.

This project is thereby targeted at visualising makeup on users such as makeup users, and makeup artists in augmented reality affording users the ability to customise their makeup looks by employing the MediaPipe library based on the BlazeFace Algorithm. The activity diagram, sequence diagram, and class diagram, which make up the system model, using the Unified Modelling Language (UML) are also represented to document a system design. The primary methods of the makeup visualisation process employed in

this work to accomplish the stated objectives.

3.2 System Design and Software Development Life Cycle (Waterfall Model)

In software engineering, system design is a crucial phase that involves creating abstract models to present different perspectives of the system. Models of the system designed during the design process are used during requirements engineering to help explain the requirements to other system stakeholders and also guide the development of the system.

Software development is a process of creating and maintaining software applications. The software development life cycle (SDLC) is the most important element in software development. It is a methodology that depicts the necessary phases in software development. Typically, it includes various phases from preliminary development analysis to post-development software testing and evaluation (Leau *et al.*, 2012). The phases of software development are:

- i. Gathering software requirements from stakeholders.
- ii. Analysis of the software requirements.
- iii. Detailed specification of the software requirements.
- iv. Software design and implementation.
- v. Testing, deployment and maintenance.

The methodology that was adopted for this project is the waterfall model because of its simplicity. According to Bassil, (2012), the Waterfall SDLC model is a sequential software development process in which progress is regarded as flowing increasingly downwards (similar to a waterfall) and it defines consecutive phases (as shown above) that must be completed one after the other and moving to the next phase only when its preceding phase is completely done (recursive process). The waterfall model is represented as shown in Figure 3.1.

3.2 Requirement Gathering and Elicitation Phase

Software requirements express the needs and constraints that are placed upon a software product that contribute to the satisfaction of some real world application (Kotonya & Sommerville, 2000). The elicitation of requirements represents an early but continuous and critical stage in the development of software systems. Stakeholders represent the most obvious source of requirements for the system. Existing systems and processes represent another source for eliciting requirements (Zowghi & Coulin, 2005).

Users of the system would have different perceptions and so it is necessary to gather requirements for elicitation through various means such as direct and participant observation, structured and unstructured interviews, questionnaires, surveys, prototyping, card sorting, brainstorming, group discussions and so on. Structured interviews were conducted to elicit requirements from project stakeholders that would allow users to visualize makeup on the augmented reality system (See Appendix A).

In this project, features of a camera which can be found on a computer device are employed to obtain a real time video of the user's face as input. The software and hardware specifications, and techniques of the system are covered in this section.

Figure 3.1 The Waterfall Model (Bassil, 2012)

3.2.1 System Requirement Specifications (SRS)

The software requirement specification includes information about all the functional and non-functional requirements for a given piece of software and it may include a set of use cases that describe user interactions that the software system must provide. It describes how the software will behave and the functionality it offers the user. It is modelled after business requirement specifications (Coope, S., n.d.). The SRS also establishes the basis for agreement between customers and contractors on what the software product is to do, as well as what it is not expected to do. It also permits a rigorous assessment of requirements before design can begin and reduces later redesign (Abran *et al.*, 2004). Use cases are a requirements discovery technique that was first introduced in the Objectory method (Jacobson, 1993). The Unified Modelling Language (UML) now includes them as a core component. A use case, in its most basic form, names the type of interaction and the people involved in it. Then, more details explaining how the user interacts with the system are added to this. Graphical models, supplemented by text annotations, are used to define the functional requirements for the system; UML use case and sequence diagrams are commonly used (Sommerville, 2011).

The functional requirements of the augmented reality system are:

- i. The system should be able to capture the user's face in real time through the interface
- ii. The system should be able to detect only one face input
- iii. The system should be able to track the features of the face
- iv. The system should be able to identify regions on the face
- v. The system should be able to apply filters to the face in augmented reality
- vi. The system should be able to render applied makeup in augmented reality

- vii. The interface should be simple to navigate
- viii. The interface must be interactive and enjoyable for the user

While the non-functional requirements of the system are:

- i. Performance: The application should have low latency and respond quickly to user interactions, ensuring a seamless and smooth user experience during makeup visualization.
- ii. Usability: The user interface should be intuitive and easy to navigate.
- iii. Responsiveness: The application should be responsive to changes in user input, providing real time updates during makeup visualization.
- iv. Reliability: The system should be stable and bug-free.
- v. Robustness: The application should be resilient to errors and exceptions, gracefully handling unexpected situations to avoid crashes or data loss.
- vi. Time Constraint: The system is required to be completed before the end of the academic session.

3.2.2 System Stakeholders

This comprises those who will operate the software (Abran *et al.*, 2004). Stakeholders are people who have an interest in the system or are affected in some ways by the development and implementation of the system and hence must be consulted during the requirements elicitation. Typically, stakeholders include groups and individuals, internal and external to the organization (Zowghi & Coulin, 2005).

The following are the major stakeholders involved in this project.

Project Supervisor

The project supervisor provides guidance and oversight throughout the development process, ensuring that the project's objectives were met and the implementation followed best practices.

Designer

The designer is charged with creating an intuitive and user-friendly interface for the system, enhancing the user experience and aesthetics.

Developers

They are responsible for implementing the system using specified technologies, ensuring seamless integration of facial tracking and computer vision techniques for the makeup application. They include software engineer, devops engineer.

Project Manager

The project manager coordinates the project and ensures successful completion of the project within the set timeline.

Makeup Users

The makeup user is an individual or group of individuals who use makeup products and services. The makeup user is the most important and only stakeholder of the system and would be able to perform the following tasks:

- i. User can start the augmented reality system
- ii. User can interact with the system interface
- iii. User can select which regions to apply makeup on

- iv. Users can choose makeup colours to apply to selected regions
- v. User can see the available makeup colours
- vi. Users can save the output after makeup has been applied

3.2.3 Software Framework

A system framework is a high-level description of the components and structure of a system, and how they work together to achieve a specific goal or set of goals. It typically includes a description of the system's architecture, its functional components, and the data flow between these components. A well-designed system framework can help ensure that a system is scalable, maintainable, and meets the needs of its intended users.

The makeup visualisation system comprises five main components:

- I. Real time Capturing: This component will capture the video stream of the user's face in real time and feed it into the Video Processing Engine for analysis.
- II. Face Detection and Tracking: This component will detect the user's face in the video stream and track its movement as the user moves their head or changes their facial expression.
- III. Video Processing Engine: This component will analyse and modify the real time video stream of the user's face to show how different makeup looks would appear on them. The engine will use computer vision algorithms to identify facial features and apply makeup in a way that looks natural and realistic.
- IV. User Interface: This component will provide the user with a graphical interface for selecting and applying different makeup products. The user will be able to choose from a range of makeup options, such as lipstick, eyeshadow, and blush, and apply them to their real time video rendition in augmented reality.
- V. Backend Services: This component will provide the necessary infrastructure to support the makeup visualisation system. This might include hosting the system

on a cloud platform, and integrating with third-party services as needed.

3.2.4 Assumptions

The system was developed based on the following assumptions:

- i. The makeup user and the makeup artist can operate a personal computer
- ii. The skin tone of the user would not be considered
- iii. Automatic makeup recommendations would not be possible on the system
- iv. Brand makeup products would not be utilized
- v. Language support is restricted to English language only.
- vi. Only a single user can operate the system at any given time.

3.2.5 Software System

The system comprises of two main components:

- i. **Frontend:** This component is responsible for handling the user interface of the system. It was built using Streamlit Library (written with Python Language), and VSCode Editor.
- ii. **Backend:** This component will be responsible for handling the logic and processing of the system. It will be built using Python language, MediaPipe framework, OpenCV and Jupyter Notebook (before integrating with the frontend).

The following technologies are used in building the software system:

Python: is a high-level, general-purpose programming language. It is popular and can be used to develop the backend processing and integration of different system components.

MediaPipe: MediaPipe is a Google open-source and cross-platform BlazeFace

algorithm framework for building perception pipelines with AI models for inferencing, over arbitrary sensory data such as video or audio, and other reusable components. It is a framework for building multimodal applied machine learning pipelines, including features such as face detection, tracking, and pose estimation. It also facilitates the deployment of computer vision applications into demos and applications on different hardware platforms (Boesch, 2023).

Streamlit: Streamlit is a free and open-source Python-based web application framework for rapidly building interactive data science and machine learning applications. It is a Python-based library specifically designed for machine learning engineers and data-scientist. It allows one to create a stunning-looking application with minimal code.

OpenCV: is a popular computer vision library that can be used for tasks such as image processing, object detection, and facial recognition.

Jupyter Notebook: This is a web-based interactive development environment for creating and sharing documents that contain live code, equations, visualisations, and narrative text.

VSCode: an integrated development environment (IDE) for software development that provides features such as code debugging, source control integration, and syntax highlighting.

3.2.6 Hardware System Design

The hardware system design should be carefully planned and presented in a clear and concise manner to ensure that the required specifications to achieve our project objectives are met. This includes:

- i. A high-resolution camera with good low light performance. image stabilization, seamless connectivity, and support for common operating systems.
- ii. A web browser application.

- iii. A PC or laptop with a sufficient Random Access Memory (RAM) minimum of 8 GB, adequate storage, and compatibility with peripherals to ensure reliable and high-quality video performance in real time.

3.3 The Real Time Augmented Reality Visualisation System Architecture

The proposed system architecture is composed of several subsystems, including video streaming input, face detection and tracking, virtual makeup video rendering, user interface, and real time capturing. The system flowchart is shown in Figure 2.5.

3.4 Unified Modelling Language (UML)

The UML is a de facto standard for object-oriented modelling. It is widely acknowledged as the accepted method for creating software system models. A collection of many diagram formats called UML can be used to model software systems (Sommerville, 2011). The design of this system makes use of the UML class diagram, sequence diagram, activity diagram, and use case diagram.

3.4.1 Use case diagram

Use case diagrams show the interactions between a system and its environment. Use cases concentrate on system behaviour from an outside perspective. A use case describes a possible course of action for an actor. An actor is a type of entity that communicates with the system via use cases. While the use cases are inside the system boundaries, the actors are outside of it. The makeup visualisation system has been designed with the makeup user as the primary user. The system is represented by a use case diagram that shows how the makeup user interacts with each of the components to achieve their desired makeup look and can download for reference or sharing if desired as shown in Figure 3.2.

3.4.2 Activity Diagram

An activity diagram displays the system process's constituent activities as well as the control flow from one activity to the next. Several dynamic aspects of a system are commonly modelled using an activity diagram (Savage & Barclay, 2004). A flow from one activity to another in the system is depicted by an activity diagram. An activity is a task carried out by the system that is accompanied by restrictions and criteria. Figure 3.3 shows the activity diagram of the system.

Figure 3.2 Use Case Diagram

Figure 3.3 Activity Diagram

3.5 Sequence Diagram

Sequence diagrams show interactions between actors and the system, and between system components. It depicts the flow of messages and actions between the objects involved in a particular scenario. The sequence diagram for the proposed system is shown in Figure 3.4.

3.6 Class Diagram

A class diagram is a type of UML diagram that depicts the structure of a system by showing the system objects' classes, their attributes, and the relationships among the classes.

In a class diagram, each class is represented as a box that includes the class name, its attributes, and its methods. The relationships between classes are shown as lines connecting the boxes. There are several types of relationships that can be depicted in a class diagram, including inheritance, association, aggregation, and composition. The class diagram for the proposed system is represented in Figure 3.5.

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Figure 3.4 Sequence Diagram

Figure 3.5 Class Diagram

3.7 Testing

White box testing is conducted to verify the functionality of each component before it is integrated into the system.

Once all components have been tested and validated, they are integrated into the system as a whole. Functional testing is conducted to ensure that the system meets the requirements and specifications laid out in the design phase. Any errors or bugs are identified, and necessary changes are made before the system is interfaced with the user interface. Once functional testing is completed, user acceptance testing is conducted to ensure the system meets the user's requirements and is easy to use.

During the testing phase, the system was put through a series of tests to ensure that it is functioning correctly. This functional method of testing includes unit testing, integration testing, system testing, and acceptance testing. Unit testing was used to test individual components and modules, while integration testing was employed to test the interaction between different components and modules. System testing was used to test the system as a whole, and user acceptance testing was utilised to ensure that the system meets the requirements of the stakeholders.

3.8 Deployment and Maintenance

After the development phase, the system is ready for deployment and use by makeup users and other relevant stakeholders in the cosmetic makeup industry. During the deployment process, support is provided to the user, including necessary training to ensure they can use the new system effectively.

Once the system is in production, maintenance becomes a critical aspect of its lifecycle. Regular maintenance helps ensure that the system operates correctly and any faults are identified and fixed promptly to prevent any potential downtime. The DevOps engineer

is responsible for maintaining the system until the end of its lifecycle. It is necessary to conduct regular reviews of the system to ensure it remains in top operational condition and prevent any potential faults.

CHAPTER FOUR

4. IMPLEMENTATION AND EVALUATION

4.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the implementation of the augmented reality makeup visualisation system, the structure of the system, the graphical user interface, and system testing. The software resources used for development of the system are stated and detailed descriptions of the results achieved from evaluation are given.

4.2 Application Modules (Development Stages)

During the implementation phase, each subsystem identified during the design phase is broken down into modules and components, and code is written for each of them. The system is designed with a user-friendly interface that allows users to select and apply different makeup styles easily.

4.2.1 Real Time Input Capturing

The system starts by enabling a user to capture their face in real time through the camera input. The system uses the MediaPipe library to access the camera feed and obtains the live video stream of the user's face. OpenCV library is used with Python for accessing the device's camera and for subsequent analysis of the real time video feed such as image processing (See Appendix C).

4.2.2 Face Detection and Tracking

Once the camera input is established, the system uses MediaPipe based on BlazeFace Algorithm, OpenCV and Python to perform face detection and tracking. MediaPipe's face detection module is employed to accurately detect a user's face within the captured

video stream. Then the user's face is tracked as they move or change expressions. With the help of OpenCV, the detected face and tracked face is shown on the interface (See Figure 4.1).

4.2.3 Makeup Regions Identification

The specific regions on the user's face where makeup can be applied are identified as landmark points. The points are localised using MediaPipe's FaceDetection and FaceMesh models. The identified regions include the lips, eyebrows, and other desired areas. This enables targeted makeup application on those regions. The landmark points are marked with numbers using OpenCV function. MediaPipe 0.8.6.2 Version effectively identifies 468 landmark points, of which points for desired regions can be selected from (See Figure 4.2).

The regions of the face for makeup application in this system and their corresponding identified points are highlighted in Table 4.1.

The makeup features matched with the regions are as represented in Table 4.2.

Table 4.1 Face Regions for Makeup Application and Identified Points using MediaPipe

S/N	FACE REGIONS	IDENTIFIED POINTS
1	Lips	61, 185, 40, 39, 37, 0, 267, 269, 270, 408, 415, 272, 271, 268, 12, 38, 41, 42, 191, 78, 76 (upper lips) 61, 146, 91, 181, 84, 17, 314, 405, 320, 307, 308, 324, 318, 402, 317, 14, 87, 178, 88, 95 (lower lips)
2	Cheeks	425, 205 (left and right cheeks centre points)
3	Left Eyebrow	70, 63, 105, 66, 107, 55, 65, 52, 53
4	Right Eyebrow	300, 293, 334, 296, 336, 285, 295, 282, 283
5	Face Boundary	10, 338, 297, 332, 284, 251, 389, 356, 454, 323, 361, 288, 397, 365, 379, 378, 400, 377, 152, 148, 176, 149, 150, 136, 172, 58, 132, 93, 234, 127, 162, 21, 54, 103, 67, 109

Table 4.2 Makeup Features and Corresponding Face Regions for Makeup Application

S/N	FACE REGIONS	MAKEUP FEATURE
1	Lips	Lipstick
2	Cheeks	Blush
3	Left Eyebrow	Eyebrow Fill
4	Right Eyebrow	Eyebrow Fill
5	Face Boundary	Foundation

Figure 4.1 Captured frames of original image (left) and output image (right)

Figure 4.2 Image showing the 468 landmark points (left) and a closer view of landmark points for the eyebrows regions (top right) and the outer part of the lips region (bottom right).

4.2.4 Augmented Reality Makeup and Filter Application

The next technique in the designed model is to apply virtual filters and makeup colours to the identified makeup regions. This process involves user interaction with the interface and is illustrated in Figure 4.3. By following these steps, users can practically interact with the makeup visualisation system, experiencing real time makeup application and generating customized makeup looks that suit their preferences.

4.2.4.1 Makeup Region Selection

Users can define the areas they want to enhance, such as the lips, eyes, or cheeks, using the GUI provided by Streamlit. Functions were implemented to create masks for each of the specified regions:

- i. Lip Mask: A mask that identifies and isolates the region of the lips for lipstick application.
- ii. Blush Mask: A mask that defines the area of the cheeks for blush application.
- iii. Brow Mask: A mask that isolates the eyebrows (left, right or both) for eyebrow filling.
- iv. Face Mask: A mask that covers the entire face for overall makeup foundation application.

4.2.4.2 Makeup Colour Selection

The makeup visualisation system provides an interactive interface using Streamlit, where users can select desired makeup colours for selected regions on their face. Users can experiment with different shades and tones by selecting the desired makeup colours from a colour palette.

4.2.4.3 Colour Conversion

In this project, functions were implemented to facilitate the conversion of selected colours on the interface from HEX to RGB and from RGB to BGR. The conversion to BGR is compatible with OpenCV functions used for blending filters in the makeup application process.

4.2.4.4 Image Processing Filters

The implementation uses the image processing capabilities of OpenCV to seamlessly blend the virtual makeup with the user's facial features. This step enhances the visualisation of the makeup look.

The techniques used for image enhancement by manipulating frames of video input were Gaussian blur, vignette, and add weighted blending.

Gaussian blur was used to achieve a more natural and seamless blend with the skin using `cv2.GaussianBlur()` function. The blur is applied to specific makeup regions such as lips, left and right eyebrows.

Vignette effect was used to draw attention to the focal points of the cheeks as gradient to circular mask about points created using `cv2.circle()` function.

Weighted blending is used to merge the masks representing makeup features with the original image using `cv2.addWeighted()` function to combine the images.

4.2.4.5 Rendering of Finished Makeup Look

The final step of the system is to render the chosen makeup colours onto the corresponding regions of the user's face using OpenCV. The process involves overlay of the virtual makeup with the user's face. The virtual makeup is seamlessly blended with the user's face in real time video input. By mapping and blending the effects

accurately using appropriate filters such as Gaussian blur, vignette, it creates well-defined eyebrows, natural-looking blush, foundation and enhanced lipstick. The rendered finished makeup look is displayed on the Streamlit GUI, providing immediate feedback to the user in real time.

In Figure 4.3, all the face makeup regions are selected for makeup application. The selected colours from the colour palette provided are then applied using the makeup processing techniques described earlier and rendered on the virtual input in real time producing the output of the system.

4.2.4.6 Download

Lastly, the system also provides a download functionality. This feature is facilitated by the Streamlit interface, allowing users to save their makeup looks for future reference or sharing. Once the output is saved, the user can now download the image file and save locally from their browser (See Figure 4.4).

Figure 4.3 Screen Showing All Makeup Features Applied to Face Regions using Interface

Figure 4.4 Screen Displayed on Clicking Save Look button and Download Button Appears

4.3 Evaluation and Discussion of Results

The evaluation of the Real Time Augmented Reality Makeup Visualization System is an essential step in determining the effectiveness, usability, and user satisfaction of the developed application. The system was evaluated using different forms of user acceptance testing such as alpha and beta testing.

Alpha Testing is a type of software testing performed to identify bugs before releasing the product to real users or to the public. Alpha testing was carried out during every phase of the system developed to ensure that all the modules are functioning as expected. Bugs encountered in some modules were fixed. For example, the overlapping eyebrows issue. During the alpha testing phase, various metrics were employed for system evaluation. Face tracking analysis was performed using percentage of successfully tracked frames.

Beta Testing is performed by real users of the software application in a real environment. It is used to gather feedback and identify any remaining issues or areas for improvement. The feedback received during beta testing was used to make final refinements and enhancements to the system before its full release. In this step, the eyebrows were refined to look more realistic. This kind of testing was conducted using a combination of methods, including face landmark analysis, user engagement level assessment, and a feedback form to determine the most frequently used makeup features and estimate the success rate of makeup application.

During the user testing phase, a group of 11 female participants was involved in the evaluation of the system. This focused on assessing accuracy, frequency of interaction, and user engagement levels among the participants. Questionnaires were also administered online.

4.3.1 Face Tracking Analysis

The primary metric used was the percentage of successfully tracked frames, which measured the system's ability to accurately track facial features under different scenarios, including alternating movements, and variations in interactivity. The frames processed by the MediaPipe Face Tracking Algorithm were recorded, and the number of frames processed per second (FPS) was measured. A minimum threshold of 15 FPS was set to determine the success rate, indicating successful tracking when FPS exceeded this threshold.

Alternating movements yielded an average success rate of 6% and 5.5 FPS, peaking at 45.8% and 504 frames. No user interaction showed improved results, with a 40.8% success rate and 12.3 FPS, reaching a peak of 66% and 639 frames. User interaction resulted in a 26.7% success rate and 12.2 FPS, with a peak of 66.7% and 522 frames. While accuracy increased with user interaction, FPS varied due to camera flickering and dynamic movements.

As seen in Figures 4.5 and 4.6, it was observed that the success rate of the system increased progressively over time as user interaction took place. As users engaged with the application and interacted with different makeup options, the system's accuracy in tracking facial features improved. However, it was noted that the FPS decreased as the total number of frames increased, primarily due to camera flickering, resulting in fluctuations in FPS. This means that the system was more successful in accurately tracking facial features when users were not moving.

During user interaction, the FPS increased, showing higher processing speed for tracking facial features. The success rate of frame tracking decreased on the left side of the graph as FPS increased, while on the right side, when users were not actively interacting and remained still, the FPS decreased, indicating lower processing speed

Figure 4.5 Plots showing success rate of frames and FPS in the presence and absence of user interaction

Figure 4.6 Plots showing success rate of frames and FPS in the presence of user interaction and variations in movement respectively

during less dynamic facial movements and the success rate of frame tracking increased.

4.3.2 Accuracy of AR Makeup Application

The evaluation of the system effectiveness was carried out by distributing a feedback form to the participants (See Appendix E). During the user testing phase, participants tried out different makeup styles on various facial regions using the application. The success rate for each makeup application was calculated based on how well the virtual makeup aligned with the user's actual facial features (See Table 4.3).

The success rate indicates the accuracy of the makeup application and is represented by percentages.

- i. **100%**: represents a perfectly aligned makeup
- ii. **95%**: represents a slightly misaligned makeup
- iii. **90%**: represents a well-aligned makeup
- iv. **80%**: represents a moderately aligned makeup
- v. **Below 80%**: represents a misaligned makeup

Based on the data sample collected, the overall average success rate for the makeup application was found to be 91.36%. This indicates that the majority of makeup applications achieved a well-aligned result, with only a few instances of slight misalignment. The system demonstrated a considerable level of accuracy and effectiveness in applying virtual makeup to different facial regions.

4.3.3 Frequency of Interaction with AR Makeup application

Analysis of the number of interactions of all participants with each makeup feature was also carried out to determine the most popular makeup feature among users of the application. The table data collected was updated with the most makeup feature used per participant (See Table 4.4).

Table 4.3 Sample Data Collected for Measurement of System Accuracy Metric

Sample	Makeup Applied per Facial Region					Virtual	Success
User Count	Lips	Cheeks	Left Eyebrow	Right Eyebrow	Face Boundary	Makeup Alignment	Rate
1	Pink lipstick	-	Brown Eyebrow filler	Black Eyebrow filler	Grey foundation	Slightly misaligned	95%
2	Purple lipstick	-	Purple Eyebrow filler	Purple Eyebrow filler	-	Significantly misaligned	80%
3	Red lipstick	Yellow blush	Brown Eyebrow filler	Brown Eyebrow filler	Pink foundation	Well aligned	90%
4	Red lipstick	Orange blush	Black Eyebrow filler	Black Eyebrow filler	Coffee brown foundation	Slightly misaligned	95%
5	Pink lipstick	Brown blush	Grey Eyebrow filler	Grey Eyebrow filler	Brown foundation	Slightly misaligned	95%

6	Red lipstick	Red blush	Black Eyebrow filler	Black Eyebrow filler	Brown foundation	Well aligned	90%
7	Brown lipstick	Red blush	Yellow Eyebrow filler	Yellow Eyebrow filler	Brown foundation	Well aligned	90%
8	Red lipstick	Red blush	White Eyebrow filler	White Eyebrow filler	Brown foundation	Slightly misaligned	95%
9	Green lipstick	Pink blush	Brown Eyebrow filler	Brown Eyebrow filler	Yellow foundation	Well aligned	90%
10	Pink lipstick	Nude blush	Black Eyebrow filler	Black Eyebrow filler	Green foundation	Well aligned	90%
11	Orange lipstick	Brown blush	Orange Eyebrow filler	Orange Eyebrow filler	Brown foundation	Slightly misaligned	95%

Table 4.4 Updated Sample Data Collected for Measurement of Number of Interactions of Makeup Feature

Sample	Makeup Feature / Number of Interactions				Most Used Makeup Feature
User Count	Lipstick	Blush	Foundation	Eyebrow Filler	
1	2	-	1	-	Lipstick
2	1	-	-	2	Eyebrow Filler
3	4	2	1	5	Eyebrow Filler
4	4	3	3	5	Eyebrow Filler
5	2	1	1	1	Lipstick
6	2	2	3	3	Foundation, Eyebrow Filler
7	3	1	2	4	Eyebrow Filler
8	3	2	1	1	Lipstick
9	3	2	2	3	Lipstick, Eyebrow Filler
10	3	2	1	2	Lipstick
11	3	5	5	8	Eyebrow Filler

Based on the data in Table 4.4, it is evident that the most frequently used makeup feature among the participants is **Eyebrow Filler**. Participants interacted with the eyebrow filler feature the most, indicating a preference for experimenting with different eyebrow styles and effects. **Lipstick** was the next most used feature with several participants selecting different lipstick shades during the testing phase.

However, some participants explored multiple makeup features, such as combining lipstick with eyebrow filler or foundation with eyebrow filler. Hence, the application provided a versatile and engaging makeup visualisation experience, satisfying the requirements of the system.

4.3.4 User Engagement Level

The user engagement level was assessed based on specific facial expressions and interactions observed during the makeup visualization process. The metrics involved in the assessment were represented as follows:

- i. Eye Gaze Direction: Indicates the dominant direction of the user's eye gaze during makeup visualization e.g., forward, sideways, backward
- ii. Eyebrow Movement: Shows the movement of the user's eyebrows while trying on makeup (e.g., raised, furrowed, neutral).
- iii. Lip Curvature: Represents the shape or curvature of the user's lips during the makeup visualization process (e.g., smiling, pursed, neutral).
- iv. Smile Intensity: Indicates the intensity of the user's smile while interacting with the makeup application (e.g., low, medium, high).

These helped categorize the engagement level into high, medium or low.

The evaluation of user engagement levels in the AR makeup visualisation application

revealed that a substantial majority of users exhibited a "High" level of engagement during the makeup try-on process (See Table 4.5). This engaged user group demonstrated consistent patterns, including a forward eye gaze direction, raised eyebrows, smiling lip curvature, and a high smile intensity. Their active and enthusiastic interaction with the virtual makeup showcased strong interest and positive emotional responses to the application, ensuring an enjoyable and immersive makeup visualisation experience.

On the other hand, a smaller segment of users displayed a "Low" level of engagement, characterized by sideways or downward eye gaze direction, furrowed eyebrows, pursed or neutral lip curvature, and a low smile intensity. This group appeared to be less invested or emotionally connected to the makeup try-on process, leading to reduced engagement levels with the application.

The findings highlight that the AR makeup visualization application was successful in engaging a significant portion of users, making them actively participate in the virtual makeup experience.

Table 4.5 Sample Data collected for Face Landmark Analysis during user testing phase

Sample	Metrics				Engagement Level
User Count	Eye Gaze Direction	Eyebrow movement	Lip Curvature	Smile Intensity	
1	forward	raised	smiling	high	high
2	forward	raised	pursed	high	high
3	forward	furrowed	smiling	medium	medium
4	sideways	furrowed	pursed	medium	low
5	forward	raised	pursed	high	high
6	forward	raised	neutral	medium	medium
7	sideways	neutral	neutral	low	low
8	forward	raised	neutral	low	low
9	downward	furrowed	pursed	low	low
10	forward	raised	smiling	medium	medium
11	downward	neutral	neutral	low	low

4.3.5 Usability Survey

An online questionnaire was administered using Google Forms to evaluate the usability and user satisfaction of the system (See Appendix D). It included Likert-style questions presented on a scale ranging from 1 to 5, with 1 representing "Strongly Disagree" and 5 representing "Strongly Agree". The questionnaire garnered responses from approximately 20 respondents, with age ranges spanning from 13-19 to above 35. The obtained data was then analysed to derive the following results:

4.3.5.1 User Experience Evaluation

Regarding the user experience evaluation, the participants rated the application highly in terms of ease of use, makeup visualization realism, and responsiveness. They appreciated the diverse and appealing virtual makeup options, which allowed them to create personalized makeup looks. Most participants were satisfied with the performance and speed of the application, although a few suggested improvements to enhance the response time for a smoother experience (See Figures 4.7 to 4.10).

4.3.5.2 Makeup Application Accuracy

The makeup application accuracy received positive feedback, with a majority of the participants indicating well-aligned makeup application for various facial regions. The eyebrow filler option was frequently used and well-received by many participants, highlighting its significance in the application's success (See Figures 4.11 and 4.12).

4.3.5.3 Application Usability and User Satisfaction

Overall, the participants showed a positive response to the application's usability and functionality. They found the application easy to use, navigate, and experiment with various makeup options (See Figures 4.13 and 4.14).

Most participants expressed a willingness to try out makeup looks tested and saved on the AR makeup app and considered using the app regularly to explore different makeup styles for various occasions.

Figure 4.7 Distribution of Users Based on Years of Experience in the Makeup Industry

Figure 4.8 Distribution of Users' Daily Makeup Usage for School or Work

Figure 4.9 Distribution of User Responses Regarding Application Ease of Use and Navigation

Figure 4.10 Distribution of User Responses to the Application's Responsiveness and Smooth Interaction

Figure 4.11 Distribution of Users' Responses to Virtual Makeup Alignment with Facial Features

Figure 4.12 Distribution of User's Responses to Virtual Makeup Suitability for Facial Skin Tone and Shape

Figure 4.13 Distribution of Users' Responses to the Ease of Understanding and Use of Makeup Visualization Tools and Features

Figure 4.14 Distribution of User Responses to Real Time Visualization's Accuracy and Responsiveness

CHAPTER FIVE

5. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

5.1 SUMMARY

This project work has presented a real time augmented reality makeup visualisation system to achieve its aim of providing users with a real time makeup simulation tool. The methodologies employed were designed to match the project's objectives, which included eliciting requirements, designing the system architecture, implementing the makeup visualization system, and evaluating its performance.

The structured interviews conducted with stakeholders allowed an understanding of potential areas of inquiry and establish the project's requirements, ensuring that the system met user needs and preferences. The Unified Modelling Language (UML) diagrams were instrumental in designing the system's architecture, providing a clear representation of its components and functionalities.

The implementation was achieved using MediaPipe and OpenCV libraries with the Python programming language and Streamlit library to create a user-friendly interface for the augmented reality makeup visualization system.

Furthermore, the results obtained from the evaluation of the system indicate its practicality and effectiveness in enhancing the user's makeup visualisation experience. The evaluation of the system's performance using metrics such as face landmark analysis, usability, and user feedback provided valuable insights into its effectiveness and user satisfaction. The results of the engagement level analysis complement the overall positive feedback received from the online questionnaire and usability testing. The high average success rate, user-friendliness, and popularity among both male and

female makeup enthusiasts underscore the system's practicality and potential impact. The evaluation of the Real Time Augmented Reality Makeup Visualization System has provided valuable insights into its performance, user engagement level, and user satisfaction. The data collected from face motion and tracking analysis revealed an average success rate of 91.8% for makeup application alignment, indicating that the application performs well in accurately applying virtual makeup to users' faces.

5.2 LIMITATIONS

One of the primary challenges was related to OpenCV execution issues, which occasionally resulted in unexpected errors and system freezes. Additionally, difficulties were faced in simultaneously colouring both eyebrows due to their overlapping region, making it challenging to achieve precise and accurate makeup application.

Another significant challenge was the tracking accuracy, which was affected by the object image dimensions and varying brightness levels. This impacted the system's ability to accurately detect and track facial features, leading to misalignments and inaccuracies in virtual makeup application.

Furthermore, it was observed that the live feed produced less stable output compared to a static video when applying makeup effects. The dynamic nature of real time video input made it more challenging to maintain consistent and stable makeup visualization, leading to occasional discrepancies in the applied makeup.

5.3 RECOMMENDATIONS

The knowledge gained from this project contributes to the advancement of augmented reality makeup technology providing a foundation for future research and development in the field.

Based on suggestions from user open-ended feedback from the questionnaire, future improvements could focus on optimizing the system for mobile devices and further enhancing the face boundary (foundation) for improved efficiency. Also, by addressing the factors contributing to lower engagement, the application can cater to a broader range of users, ensuring a more enjoyable and engaging experience for all.

The developed system is relevant across various application domains, making it a valuable asset in sectors like education and the cosmetic industry.

In the education sector, the system's interactive makeup visualization can serve as a powerful tool for makeup artists in training. Students can practice and experiment with different makeup looks on virtual models, honing their skills in a risk-free environment. This approach allows for continuous learning and improvement, aiding in the development of makeup artists' expertise. Additionally, the system can be integrated into beauty and cosmetology courses, offering students a hands-on experience that aligns with industry trends and demands.

Furthermore, within the cosmetic industry, the system can revolutionize the way consumers interact with makeup products. Cosmetic brands can integrate the technology into their websites or mobile applications, allowing customers to virtually try-on products before making a purchase. This eliminates the need for physical sampling, reducing waste (**SDG #12 - Responsible Consumption and Production**) and enhancing the overall shopping experience. Users can confidently explore various makeup looks and products, leading to more informed purchasing decisions and customer satisfaction.

In conclusion, the developed makeup visualization system holds immense potential for diverse application areas, including education and the cosmetic industry. Its versatility

and interactive nature make it a valuable asset that can shape the future of makeup artistry, training, and consumer engagement. As the technology continues to evolve, it has the potential to reshape how makeup is learned, practiced, and enjoyed across diverse sectors.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A - Interview Guide

INTERVIEW GUIDE – 15 minutes each

- **Introduction**

Who you are and reason for interview, response usage and confidentiality

- **Questions**

1. Understanding User Needs

- ❖ Frequency of makeup usage
- ❖ Main challenges when trying out makeup styles
- ❖ Experimental try on versus product purchases
- ❖ Need for personalization
- ❖ Tools for makeup application and likely features of application
- ❖ Need for identified makeup features
- ❖ Makeup Visualization prospects

2. User Interface and Interactivity

- ❖ Need for ease of use in application
- ❖ Important elements for an intuitive and interactive user interface
- ❖ Makeup simulation preference (static or real time)
- ❖ Customization Features

3. Accuracy

- ❖ Importance of Virtual Makeup Alignment
- ❖ Special attention areas during makeup application

4. Development Platform - Specific requirements or limitations

5. Download Functionality - Importance

6. Suggestions

- ❖ Any additional comments, or concerns about the application

- **Conclusion**

Appreciation and further communication.

APPENDIX B - Program listing

Landmarks Identification (main/landmarks.py)

```
import cv2

import numpy as np

from typing import List, Iterable

from mediapipe.python.solutions.face_mesh import FaceMesh

def detect_landmarks(src: np.ndarray, is_stream: bool = False):
    """
    Given an image `src` retrieves the facial landmarks associated with it
    """
    with FaceMesh(static_image_mode=not is_stream, max_num_faces=1,
min_detection_confidence=0.6, min_tracking_confidence=0.6) as face_mesh:
        src = cv2.cvtColor(src, cv2.COLOR_BGR2RGB)

        results = face_mesh.process(src)

        if results.multi_face_landmarks: # type: ignore

            return results.multi_face_landmarks[0].landmark # type: ignore

def normalize_landmarks(landmarks, height: int, width: int, mask: Iterable = None): #
type: ignore
    """
    The landmarks returned by mediapipe have coordinates between [0, 1].

    This function normalizes them in the range of the image dimensions so they can
be played with.
```

```

"""

normalized_landmarks = np.array(
    [(int(landmark.x * width), int(landmark.y * height)) for landmark in landmarks])

if mask:

    normalized_landmarks = normalized_landmarks[mask] # type: ignore

return normalized_landmarks

def plot_landmarks(src: np.ndarray, landmarks: List, show: bool = False): # type:
ignore
    """

    Given a source image and a list of landmarks plots them onto the image

    """

    dst = src.copy()

    for x, y in landmarks:

        cv2.circle(dst, (x, y), 2, 0, cv2.FILLED)

    if show:

        print("Displaying image plotted with landmarks")

        # cv2.imshow("Plotted Landmarks", dst)

    return dst

```

Masks for Makeup Regions (main/segments.py)

```

from utils import *

```

```

def lip_mask(src: np.ndarray, points: np.ndarray, color: list):
    """
    Given a src image, points of lips and a desired color
    Returns a colored mask that can be added to the src
    """
    mask = np.zeros_like(src) # Create a mask

    # Mask for the required facial feature
    mask = cv2.fillPoly(mask, [points], color)

    # Blurring the region, so it looks natural
    mask = cv2.GaussianBlur(mask, (7, 7), 10)

    return mask

def brow_mask(src: np.ndarray, points: np.ndarray, color: list):
    mask = np.zeros_like(src)

    mask = cv2.fillPoly(mask, [points], color)

    mask = cv2.GaussianBlur(mask, (7, 7), 10)

    return mask

def face2_mask(src: np.ndarray, points: np.ndarray, color: list):
    mask = np.zeros_like(src)

    mask = cv2.fillPoly(mask, [points], color)

    mask = cv2.GaussianBlur(mask, (7, 7), 5)

    return mask

def blush_mask(src: np.ndarray, points: np.ndarray, color: list, radius: int):

```

```

"""

Given a src image, points of the cheeks, desired color and radius

Returns a colored mask that can be added to the src

"""

mask = np.zeros_like(src) # Mask that will be used for the cheeks

for point in points:

    # Blush => Color filled circle

    mask = cv2.circle(mask, point, radius, color, cv2.FILLED)

    x, y = point[0] - radius, point[1] - radius # Get the top-left of the mask

    mask[y:y + 2 * radius, x:x + 2 * radius] = vignette(mask[y:y + 2 * radius, x:x + 2
* radius],

                                20) # Vignette on the mask

    return mask

def face_mask(src: np.ndarray, points: np.ndarray):

    """

    Given a list of face landmarks, return a closed polygon mask for the same

    """

    mask = np.zeros_like(src)

    mask = cv2.fillPoly(mask, [points], (255, 255, 255))

    return mask

def vignette(src: np.ndarray, sigma: int):

    """

```

Given a src image and a sigma, returns a vignette of the src

```
"""  
  
height, width, _ = src.shape  
  
kernel_x = cv2.getGaussianKernel(width, sigma)  
  
kernel_y = cv2.getGaussianKernel(height, sigma)  
  
  
kernel = kernel_y * kernel_x.T  
  
mask = kernel / kernel.max()  
  
blurred = cv2.convertScaleAbs(src.copy() * np.expand_dims(mask, axis=-1))  
  
return blurred
```

Makeup Features Application (main/apply_makeup.py)

```
from utils import *  
  
from landmarks import detect_landmarks, normalize_landmarks, plot_landmarks  
  
from segments import lip_mask, brow_mask, face2_mask, blush_mask  
  
  
def apply_all_makeup(src: np.ndarray, is_stream: bool, features: list, show_landmarks:  
bool = False):  
  
    """  
  
    Takes in a source image and applies effects onto it.  
  
    """  
  
    ret_landmarks = detect_landmarks(src, is_stream)  
  
    height, width, _ = src.shape
```

```

if ret_landmarks is not None:

feature_landmarks = normalize_landmarks(ret_landmarks, height, width)

output = src.copy()

for feature in features:

if feature['name'] == 'lips':

    lip_landmarks = normalize_landmarks(

ret_landmarks, height, width, upper_lip + lower_lip)

    mask = lip_mask(output, lip_landmarks, feature['color'])

    output = cv2.addWeighted(output, 1.0, mask, 0.4, 0.0)

elif feature['name'] == 'lbrow':

    lbrow_landmarks = normalize_landmarks(

ret_landmarks, height, width, left_brow)

    mask = brow_mask(output, lbrow_landmarks, feature['color'])

    output = cv2.addWeighted(output, 1.0, mask, 0.4, 0.0)

elif feature['name'] == 'rbrow':

    rbrow_landmarks = normalize_landmarks(

ret_landmarks, height, width, right_brow)

    mask = brow_mask(output, rbrow_landmarks, feature['color'])

    output = cv2.addWeighted(output, 1.0, mask, 0.4, 0.0)

elif feature['name'] == 'blush':

    blush_landmarks = normalize_landmarks(

ret_landmarks, height, width, cheeks)

```

```

        mask = blush_mask(output, blush_landmarks,
                           feature['color'], 50)

        output = cv2.addWeighted(output, 1.0, mask, 0.3, 0.0)

    elif feature['name'] == 'foundation':

        face_landmarks = normalize_landmarks(ret_landmarks, height, width,
face_conn)

        mask = face2_mask(output, face_landmarks, feature['color'])

        output = cv2.addWeighted(output, 1.0, mask, 0.3, 0.0)

    if show_landmarks:

        output = plot_landmarks(output, feature_landmarks, True) # type: ignore

    return output

else:

    print("No landmarks detected.")

```

USER INTERFACE

Region for Selection (main/regions.py)

```

makeup_segments = [

    'SELECT REGION',

    'LEFT EYEBROW ONLY',

    'RIGHT EYEBROW ONLY',

    'LEFT EYEBROW, RIGHT EYEBROW',

    'BOTH EYEBROWS',

    'BOTH CHEEKS',

```

```
'FACE BOUNDARY',  
  
'LIPS',  
  
'LIPS AND CHEEKS',  
  
'EYEBROWS AND CHEEKS',  
  
'EYEBROWS AND LIPS',  
  
'EYEBROWS, LIPS AND CHEEKS',  
  
'EYEBROWS AND FACE BOUNDARY',  
  
'FACE BOUNDARY AND LIPS',  
  
'FACE BOUNDARY AND CHEEKS',  
  
'FACE BOUNDARY AND EYEBROWS',  
  
'FACE BOUNDARY, EYEBROWS AND CHEEKS',  
  
'FACE BOUNDARY, EYEBROWS AND LIPS',  
  
'FACE BOUNDARY, LIPS AND CHEEKS',  
  
'ALL MAKEUP REGIONS (EYEBROWS, FACE BOUNDARY, CHEEKS, and  
LIPS)'  
]
```

Color Conversion from HEX TO RGB, RGB TO BGR

(main/color_conversion.py)

```
def hex_to_rgb(hex_value):  
  
    # Remove the '#' symbol if present  
  
    hex_value = hex_value.lstrip('#')  
  
    # Convert hexadecimal to decimal
```

```
    red = int(hex_value[0:2], 16)

    green = int(hex_value[2:4], 16)

    blue = int(hex_value[4:6], 16)

    return [red, green, blue]

def rgb_to_bgr(rgb_value):

    r, g, b = rgb_value

    bgr_value = [b, g, r]

    return bgr_value
```

START UP STREAMLIT GUI (main/zenup_makeup.py)

```
# AR MAKEUP VISUALIZATION APPLICATION INTERFACE WITH
STREAMLIT

import streamlit as app

import mediapipe as mp

import cv2

import numpy as np

import tempfile

import time

from PIL import Image, ImageColor, ImageGrab

import csv

import os

from landmarks import *
```

```

from apply_makeup import *

from utils import *

from regions import makeup_segments

from color_conversion import *

mp_drawing = mp.solutions.drawing_utils

mp_face_mesh = mp.solutions.face_mesh

app.title("").markdown("<div style='background-color:#160926; margin-top:-40px;
margin-left:-80px; margin-right:-80px; height:80px; display: flex; justify-content:
center; align-items: center;'><h3 style='font-family: Inter; color:#ffffff; font-size:
36px; font-weight: 700; text-transform: uppercase'>ZEN UP 🤖</h3></div>",
unsafe_allow_html=True) # 🏠

app.markdown(
    """
    <style>
    [data-testid="stSidebar"] {
    background-color: #DBC7F4;
    }
    [data-testid="stSidebar"][aria-expanded="true"] > div:first-child {
    width: 350px;
    }
    """

```

```

    [data-testid="stSidebar"][aria-expanded="false"] > div:first-child {

width: 350px;

margin-left: -350px;

    }

</style>

"",

unsafe_allow_html=True
)

app.sidebar.title('INTERACTIONS')

app.sidebar.markdown('---')

app.sidebar.subheader('MAKEUP REGIONS')

@app.cache_data(ttl=24*3600)

@app.cache_resource(ttl=24*3600)

def image_resize(image, width=None, height=None, inter = cv2.INTER_AREA):

    dim = None

    (h, w) = image.shape[:2]

    if width is None and height is None:

        return image

```

```

if width is None:

    # r = ()

    dim = (int((w * width) / float(w)), height)

else:

    r = width/float(w)

    dim = (width, int(h * r));

# resize the image

resized = cv2.resize(image, dim, interpolation=inter)

return resized

makeup_region = app.sidebar.selectbox('Select Region to Apply Makeup',
makeup_segments)

app.sidebar.markdown('---')

app.sidebar.subheader('SHADES')

app.sidebar.write(f"<h5 style='text-align: center; font-weight: 300; color: black; text-align: left;'>Select Colour to Apply</h5>", unsafe_allow_html=True)

makeup = [];

if makeup_region is not None:

    if ('LEFT EYEBROW' in makeup_region):

        left_eyebrow_colour = app.sidebar.color_picker(

            "LEFT EYEBROW FILL COLOUR", value="#ffff00", key="LEY")

        makeup.append({"name": "lbrow", "color":

```

```

rgb_to_bgr(hex_to_rgb(left_eyebrow_colour)))

    if ('RIGHT EYEBROW' in makeup_region):

        right_eyebrow_colour = app.sidebar.color_picker(

            "RIGHT EYEBROW FILL COLOUR", value="#ff00ff", key="REY")

        makeup.append({"name": "rbrow", "color":
rgb_to_bgr(hex_to_rgb(right_eyebrow_colour)))

    if ('EYEBROWS' in makeup_region):

        eyebrows_colour = right_eyebrow_colour = app.sidebar.color_picker(

            "EYEBROWS FILL COLOUR", value="#ffff0", key="LEY")

        makeup.append({"name": "lbrow", "color":
rgb_to_bgr(hex_to_rgb(eyebrows_colour)))

        makeup.append({"name": "rbrow", "color":
rgb_to_bgr(hex_to_rgb(eyebrows_colour)))

    if ('CHEEKS' in makeup_region):

        blush_colour = app.sidebar.color_picker(

            "BLUSH COLOUR", value="#fff010", key="CH")

        makeup.append({"name": "blush", "color":
rgb_to_bgr(hex_to_rgb(blush_colour)))

    if ('FACE BOUNDARY' in makeup_region):

```

```

foundation_colour = app.sidebar.color_picker(
    "FOUNDATION COLOUR", value="#00ff10", key="FB")

makeup.append({"name": "foundation", "color":
rgb_to_bgr(hex_to_rgb(foundation_colour))})

if ('LIPS' in makeup_region):

    lipstick_colour = app.sidebar.color_picker(
        "LIPSTICK COLOUR", value="#0fffa0", key="LI")

    makeup.append({"name": "lips", "color":
rgb_to_bgr(hex_to_rgb(lipstick_colour))})

    apply_button = app.sidebar.button('Apply Makeup', disabled=False)

    app.markdown("<h3 style='font-family: Inter; color:#160926; font-size: 24px;
font-weight: 700; text-transform: uppercase'>RENDERING FEED</h3>",
unsafe_allow_html=True)

app.sidebar.markdown('---')

path = r"media/videos/video-detect.mp4"

vid2Frame = app.empty();

vid2 = cv2.VideoCapture(0)

width2 = int(vid2.get(cv2.CAP_PROP_FRAME_WIDTH))

height2 = int(vid2.get(cv2.CAP_PROP_FRAME_HEIGHT))

```

```

fps_input2 = int(vid2.get(cv2.CAP_PROP_FPS))

# app.markdown("**Frame Rate (FPS)**")

# app.write(f"<h1 style='text-align: center; color:
blue;'>{fps_input2}</h1>",unsafe_allow_html=True)

# recording

codec2 = cv2.VideoWriter_fourcc('V', 'P', '0', '9') # type: ignore
out2 = cv2.VideoWriter('media/videos/output/out2.mp4', codec2, fps_input2, (width2,
height2))

fps2 = 0
i2 = 0
download_button = app.button('Save Look', disabled=False)

if apply_button:
    app.success('Makeup Rendered', icon="✅")
    app.markdown("<hr />", unsafe_allow_html=True)

prevTime = 0

# Initialize variables

total_frames = 0

successful_frames = 0

```

```
threshold_fps = 15 # Set your desired threshold FPS value

screenshot_count = 0

show_points = False

# loop to stream video frames

while vid2.isOpened():

    i2+= 1

    try:

        ret_val, frame2 = vid2.read()

        frame2 = cv2.flip(frame2, 1)

        if ret_val:

            features = [];

            if (apply_button):

                features = makeup;

            feat_applied = apply_all_makeup(frame2, True, features, show_points)

            if cv2.waitKey(1) == 27:

                break

        try:

            frame2 = cv2.resize(feat_applied, (0,0), fx=0.8, fy=0.8)

            frame2 = image_resize(image=frame2,width=640)
```

```

if download_button:

    screenshot_count += 1;

    # filename = f"zenup_look_{screenshot_count}.jpg"

    filename = f"zenup_look.jpg"

    cv2.imwrite(filename, frame2)

    app.download_button(label='Download', data=open(filename, 'rb'),
file_name=filename)

    # os.remove(filename)

    break

# if show_points is False:

#     if(app.sidebar.button('view landmarks', help='Control landmarks after
applying makeup')):

#         show_points = not show_points

except Exception:

    print("Failed to resize")

    pass

except Exception:

    print("An error occurred")

    pass

# FPS counter

currTime = time.time()

```

```

fps = 1 / (currTime - prevTime)

prevTime = currTime

# Test

# Check if FPS exceeds the threshold

if fps > threshold_fps:

    successful_frames += 1

    total_frames += 1

    # app.write(f"<h1 style='text-align: center; color: blue;'>{int(fps)}</h1>",
unsafe_allow_html=True)

# Calculate percentage of successfully tracked frames

success_rate = (successful_frames / total_frames) * 100

print(f"Percentage of successfully tracked frames: {success_rate:.2f}%")

# # WRITE DATA INTO FILE

# data = [successful_frames, total_frames,int(fps), round(success_rate, 2)]

# # Open the CSV file in append mode and create a CSV writer object

# filename = 'data-movement.csv'

# with open(filename, 'a', newline=") as csvfile:

#     csvwriter = csv.writer(csvfile)

```

```
# # Write the data as a new row in the CSV file

# csvwriter.writerow(data)

# # Close the file after writing

# csvfile.close()

vid2Frame.image(frame2, channels='BGR', use_column_width=True)

vid2.release()

out2.release()

cv2.destroyAllWindows()
```

APPENDIX C - Sample of Camera Input Rendered on the User Interface

ZEN UP APPLICATION USABILITY TESTING

Dear Respondent,

I, Mariam Omoriyeba Adekola, an undergraduate student of Obafemi Awolowo University, pursuing a degree in Computer Engineering is conducting a usability survey as part of my final year project. This questionnaire aims to assess user satisfaction with the **Real Time Augmented Reality (AR) Makeup Visualization System** titled "Zen Up" I have developed for the purpose of this project, focusing on user perception on makeup, user experience, real time makeup visualization improvements and recommendations.

Your valuable feedback is invaluable in evaluating the system's effectiveness and usability. Please provide your honest opinions by answering the following questions. It would take 15 minutes or less to complete.

Please be assured that your responses will be used solely for academic purposes, and your identity will be kept confidential. Your participation in this survey is entirely voluntary, and you can withdraw at any time without any negative consequences.

* Indicates required question

Demographic Information

This information helps in understanding the user demographics and their makeup background.

1. What is your age range? (in years) *

Mark only one oval.

- 13 - 19
- 20 - 24
- 25 - 29
- 30 - 35
- Above 35

2. What is your gender? *

Mark only one oval.

- Male
- Female
- Prefer not to say
- Other

3. How many years of makeup experience do you have? (if applicable)

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

None Makeup Professional (Artist or Entrepreneur)

4. On an average day going to school or work, how much makeup do you wear? *

Mark only one oval.

- None.
- Very little, foundation and lip gloss.
- Foundation, lip gloss, and a little eye makeup.
- A full face of makeup

User Perception and Preferences

These questions focus on willingness to try makeup looks, usage intentions, belief in the accuracy of virtual makeup, and confidence in customizing virtual makeup.

Rate your agreement to these statements in terms of *Yes* or *No*

5. Would you consider using the AR makeup app regularly to explore different makeup styles and trends? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No
 Maybe

6. Would you be willing to try out makeup looks tested and saved on this AR makeup app?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No
 Maybe

7. Do you think the AR makeup app could replace physical makeup try-ons in the future? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No
 Maybe

User Experience Evaluation

These questions cover aspects like ease of use, realism of makeup visualization, diversity of virtual makeup options, responsiveness, and overall satisfaction with the user experience.

On a scale from 1 to 5, rate your experience using Zen Up application (1 Strongly Disagree or Not Likely, 5 Strongly Agree or Very Likely)

8. The application was easy to use and navigate. *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

9. The makeup visualization was realistic and accurately applied.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

10. The virtual makeup features were diverse and appealing.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

11. The real time visualization provided a personalized experience. *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

12. The application was intuitive, it provided clear instructions and guidance.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

13. The application responded quickly and smoothly to my interactions. *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

14. I would use this application for trying out different makeup looks. *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

15. How likely are you to purchase makeup products directly through the AR makeup app after trying them virtually?

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

16. How likely are you to recommend this augmented reality makeup visualization application to others? *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Makeup Application Accuracy

The questions explore aspects such as alignment with facial features, ease of the application process, and natural appearance on different facial regions.

On a scale from 1 to 5, rate your agreement to these statements for assessing the accuracy of the augmented reality makeup application. (1 Strongly Disagree, 5 Strongly Agree)

17. The virtual makeup accurately aligned with my facial features.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

18. The makeup application process was straightforward and efficient. *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

19. The virtual makeup applied to different facial regions appeared natural. *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

20. I found it easy to adjust the virtual makeup to my preferences. *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

21. The virtual makeup was well-suited to my skin tone and facial shape.

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Overall Application Usability

22. Were the makeup visualization tools and features easy to understand and use? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- Maybe

23. Did the real-time visualization meet your expectations for accuracy and responsiveness? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

Maybe

Open-Ended Feedback

This section allows respondents to provide any additional comments or suggestions they have about the application. It offers an opportunity to share insights and opinions not covered in the previous sections, providing valuable feedback for further improvements.

24. Comments or Suggestions (if any)

Application Testing

Here, you can interact with the application and explore different makeup options virtually.

Try out various makeup looks and provide feedback on their experience.

Link: [Zen Up App](#)

Please take your time to explore the application and test its functionalities. After testing, I humbly request you to return to this questionnaire and share your thoughts and feedback in the previous sections.

Thank you for your participation and valuable input in testing my Real Time Augmented Reality Makeup Visualization System. Your feedback will help enhance the application for a better user experience.

Zen Up Application Sample Output

End of Questionnaire

Thank you for taking the time to complete this feedback form. Your feedback will be crucial in improving our Real Time Augmented Reality Makeup Visualization System. If you have any further comments or questions, please feel free to contact Mariam at mariam.adekola10@gmail.com.

Thank you for your time and cooperation. Your contribution is highly appreciated.

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Google Forms

APPENDIX E - User Testing Feedback Form

USER TESTING FEEDBACK FORM (DURATION - 5 MINUTES)

Dear Participant,

Thank you for participating in the user testing of the Real Time Augmented Reality Makeup Visualization System. Your feedback is essential in helping us evaluate the effectiveness and usability of the application. Please take a few minutes to provide your valuable feedback by completing this form.

FREQUENTLY USED MAKEUP FEATURE				
MAKEUP FEATURE	Lipstick	Blush	Foundation	Eyebrow Filler
NUMBER OF INTERACTIONS				

MAKEUP APPLICATION SUCCESS RATE						
FACIAL REGIONS	Lips	Cheeks	Left Eyebrow	Right Eyebrow	Face Boundary	Overall Virtual Makeup Alignment
MAKEUP APPLIED						

Virtual Makeup Alignment e.g. Perfectly aligned, aligned, moderately aligned, misaligned

Makeup Applied e.g. red lipstick, pink blush, red left eyebrow filler, blue foundation